

Foresight Through Design Thinking to Ethically Inform Strategy in Artificial Intelligence Development: Design Ethology Meets the Cyberneticists

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Abstract: Design Thinking has gained significant attention in recent years leading to permeation into a range of other disciplines, research areas and practical applications alike. Here, we focus specifically on the use of Design Thinking for the purpose of exploration and strategic decision making of not-yet fully formed concepts of novel design ideas, strategies and the likes. The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) poses pertinent questions around its utilization rivalling with Design Thinking as such an approach. Ethical considerations in this are crucial and must be considered as AI gains attention, traction and more widespread applications as a way to predict and make decisions on future directions. This article explores concepts taken from cybernetics in the consideration of ethics, ethology and expands on the utilization of design thinking and AI in foresight and maneuvering uncertain futures.

Practical Implications: This article has a role for design thinking in the navigating the field of AI as it has shown through the addressing practical implications in the early days of user interface development and should be front and center in new developments in the infancy of this emerging development in information technology.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; AI; Cybernetics; Design Ethology; Design Thinking; Ethics; Foresight

1. Introduction

Design Futures are at a crossroad with Design Thinking as a mode of practice within the business sectors other than conventionally aligned design practice, the expanding of which has brought to new disciplines to design as well as hybridized tools from social science (Eisenbart et al., 2022a). As this new market expansion brings new players, the rules of engagement shift the culture of core design ethics and practice. A community of practice approach to these new fields has seen much lay writing about design which cannot be dismissed as mere thought bubbles. By comparison the field of cybernetics has re-emerged from its conception in the mid 20th century to replant its flag in the management mainstream potentially stemming from growth in artificial intelligence (AI) in gaining control of the machine/human interface. When compared with a biophilic framework in what I have called Design Ethology, where behavior is framed against social organization and environments, a human centered construct pushes up against the flood of machine learning.

A speculation of futures as these two worlds meet is our world at present and the implications human implications need to be brought to the fore for dissection and evaluation. To allow an unbridled invasion of AI into organisations and their control over society without strong filtering of the harsher elements would be a capitulation to totalitarianism. Design,

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Design Thinking and the human filter is imperative to reap the benefits of machine learning for the benefit of the culture of humanity.

As with climate change, it has taken the world too long to recognize the gravity of the situation that human consumption has brought upon itself. Despite the science and the warnings, society has suffered push back from vested interests who stand to gain monetarily from the status quo. With the United Nations shifting the status from global warming to the era of global boiling (United Nations, 2023) and record heat and global melting, the populous are growing fearful and are calling for change.

Similarly, the world is responding to the escalation in AI models with activists withdrawing their labor in an effort to ensure their place in creative fields like writing in the film industry (Lees, 2023). With actors joining with writers to jointly call for change, the Union President, Fran Drescher says “We are all in jeopardy of being replaced by machines.” Sounding a lot like the Luddites during the industrial revolution, loss of livelihoods cuts deeper than just loss of jobs to technology it cuts into human creativity and belonging, not just a job but a part of being. Ethics plays a strong part in this discourse, investors in technology speculate billions into research in technological development which exponentially escalates the division between rich and poor (Department of Industry, Science and Resources, 2023) the counter argument rests with the expanding middle classes in the Developing nations around the globe.

But with increases in living standards and growth, comes the pressure on resources and the impact on climate, a truly existential threat to segue back to. So how do we navigate the ethics of Artificial Intelligence and the human and environmental impact? With triple bottom line development having the social added, human factors needs to expand its Information Technology bent and relate more to the equity in the labor contract, not so much the triple but the quadruple bottom line (Cambridge, 2023) to account for culture in the mix.

A webinar given by Dr. Jon Whittle (Whittle & Victoria, 2023) for the Victorian Government titled “AI: A point of inflection for the Arts” saw where a positivist perspective was given on current state, futures and set out principles for ethical engagement with AI and the future, citing here their statement on Principles at a Glance. (Department of Industry, Science and Resources, 2023):

“Human, societal and environmental wellbeing: AI systems should benefit individuals, society and the environment.

Human-centered values: AI systems should respect human rights, diversity, and the autonomy of individuals.

Fairness: AI systems should be inclusive and accessible, and should not involve or result in unfair discrimination against individuals, communities or groups.

Privacy protection and security: AI systems should respect and uphold privacy rights and data protection, and ensure the security of data.

Reliability and safety: AI systems should reliably operate in accordance with their intended purpose.

Transparency and explainability: There should be transparency and responsible disclosure so people can understand when they are being significantly impacted by AI, and can find out when an AI system is engaging with them.

Contestability: When an AI system significantly impacts a person, community, group or environment, there should be a timely process to allow people to challenge the use or outcomes of the AI system.

Accountability: People responsible for the different phases of the AI system lifecycle should be identifiable and accountable for the outcomes of the AI systems, and human oversight of AI systems should be enabled.”

Noting here that these principles in brief are a non-mandatory framework and shown here in draft format.

In this article, we review the fundamental aspects of ethology and ethics in the context laid out above, before turning our attention to anticipatory considerations, such as speculative futures, foresight and the role of design thinking in anticipating, hypothesizing and acting on potential futures in an attempt to deal with its inherent uncertainties.

2. Ethology

When compared with a biophilic framework in what has been called Design Ethology (Watson, 2014), where behavior is framed against social organization and environments, a human centered construct pushes up against the flood of machine learning. Design Thinking and advances in incorporating abductive thinking systems (Eisenbart et al., 2022b) within corporations largely off the back of developments in commercializing or socializing Information Technology platforms from MS – DOS to Windows 11/MacOS13. From a technological tool to personal computer information technology has had a bumpy ride in meeting the dual needs of industry and society.

The environmental impact of IT in terms of energy consumption too has only recently been brought to the public's attention (Lange et al., 2020) and 'absolute decoupling' is being discussed as the as the powerhouse of commerce pushes forward. Cybernetics or Human Factors are now being considered beyond the 3BL (Milne & Gray, 2012) across the quadruple bottom line of economy, environmental, social and cultural (Laragh & ElMaraghy, 2014) or profit, planet, people and now purpose.

3. Ethics

Indeed, the purpose of Artificial Intelligence needs to be addressed with rigor as commerce pushes for growth and on past performance ignorant or complicit in ramifications beyond the primary pillar of profit.

According to Soppe (2017) "The neoclassical approach [to business is] The primary objective of companies in the neoclassical vision is to maximize profits – not serving social interests. In 1970, Milton Friedman suggested in his famous article in the Financial Times : "There is one and only one social responsibility of business – to use its resources and engage in activities in such a way that it increases its profits, so long as it stays within the rules of the game, which is to say, engages in open and free competition, without deception, fraud or disobeying the law". When applied against a Liberal economic framework such as proffered by von Hayek morals have tended to slip towards the monetary.

Normative ethics consists of virtue ethics, deontology, and consequentialism. With the latter being the maximization of value, deontology being rules-based utilitarianism and virtue ethics being your best self in the division of virtue and vice. Commerce and especially that linked to Information Technology from a business development perspective has failed dismally in the navigating virtue as expressed by the divergence of wealth and leaving society behind. Muratovski (2020) frames research methodology from a design perspective when identifying methods associated with ethics and talks of "In Research we Trust" calling on a better way to conduct design thinking through design research.

4. Speculative Futures

A speculation of futures as these two philosophies meet is our world at present and the human implications need to be brought to the fore for dissection and evaluation. Profit and Purpose are at the core of engagement in 2023, so what do we see? By allowing an 'open slather' approach to Artificial Intelligence in information technology, will there be a balance of advantages in meeting ethical purpose and meaningful work for example. This is the speculation, that other areas of activity will emerge with new employment activities making up for the loss of past vocations.

Non-renewable consumption and population growth are the key drivers of a challenging future. The concept of speculation in this threat pushes up against the value of virtue and vice with greed, covetousness of other people's (consumers) capital, long identified as one of the seven capital vices or sins. To speculate is to form a theory without firm evidence but it also means to invest in the hope of gains but with the risk of loss. With reflection upon ethology (human [animal] behavior) and ethics as discussed, to gamble with society through investment in artificial information technology hopes for gains and assumes loss but is inured to societal impact as experience throughout the industrial revolution has provided new unforeseen opportunities and benefits. The positivist approach as discussed by Whittle and Victoria (2023) is cautionary as technologists push up against ethics in meeting investors.

While on a panel chaired by Prof. Katja Holtta-Otto on Innovation for Inclusivity and diversity Watson proposed the acronym DEMSTA or Design Engineering Math Science Technology & Arts, positioning Design at the front of STEM and distancing the Arts from Design. As Design effectively means 'to plan' and with Design Thinking methods widely embraced for its discovery attributes in research, Design is well positioned to assist in speculation, call it Grounded Theory or similar where abductive thinking through qualitative research is championed.

5. Foresight

In looking more closely to 'Purpose' from a rules-based perspective the current guidelines or goals proposed by the United Nations through the Sustainable Development Goals or SDGs with targets and timelines leading to the year 2030 are a system for good. The 17 goals and their correlating targets provides a structure within which organisations and individuals can concentrate their research focus on identifying key problems and formulating appropriate actions.

Bevolo (2022) states that "Foresight belongs to the realm of 'strategic thinking,' whereas the domain of 'design' is governed by the principles of 'design thinking,'" later discussing 'convergence' concluding that (Bevolo, 2022) "[AI] might put at good use the large quantities of unstructured data we create in social networks every day". This could be considered the strength of AI in its ability to sort through masses of data to identify patterns from which actions can be formulated to address issues. The problem that conventional thinking has with AI is the tendency to overreach and ask the technology to go beyond its capacity to make ethical judgements on limited data. The explosion that the world has witnessed in the past decade through agencies such as Facebook and Google mining data for profits has tripped up numerous ethical and legal debates and challenges to this business model. Design Thinking through abductive logic provides provision for an ethical lens to be utilized at the start of a project and hopefully sets parameters for safe engagement and beneficial outcomes.

6. Design Thinking Problem Setting/Solving

Exploring, creating and choosing novel design ideas successfully means not rejecting projects that will have market potential (commonly referred to as 'Type-I error') while rejecting those that will not have market potential (conversely called 'Type-II error'). The selection process usually requires collecting and assessing market demand and product cost data. However, in filtering incipient ideas for a product or service idea that is yet barely fully formed, this information is rarely available. The typical product evaluation process can drain a company's resources (Kornish & Ulrich, 2014) given that the current literature recommends decision makers assess a litany of strategic goals with any number of measures (Regner, 2003). Others propose copious scoring and ranking methods (Cooper, 1985). If companies were to apply these methods to all ideas generated, the information and evaluation criteria for aggregated set of ideas can lead to a cognitive overload (Lovallo & Sibony, 2010; Kahneman et al., 1982). Moreover, trying to evaluate the market potential of any product idea always carries an element of uncertainty.

The evaluation of the merits that concepts for new products or services may have is not necessarily limited to product selection decisions but is, in fact, a fundamental aspect of the practice of design. Strategic business management literature increasingly recommends the adoption of approaches from design thinking and related approaches and strategies for decision making on innovation (Martin, 2009; Brown, 2008). Innovative ideas cannot be evaluated with the same criteria used in the evaluation of more traditional investment process. For instance, concurrent economic theory for strategic decision making is typically based on (Subjective) Expected Utility (SEU) theory (Savage, 1954; Ellsberg, 1961). SEU involves the enumeration of possibilities, analysis of the possible outcomes, and the (objective) selection of the one utility-maximizing option (Gilboa & Schmeidler, 2001). Such a decision-making process involves the analysis and evaluation of design concepts against a series of criteria. Yet, application of SEU on early stage innovation projects is hampered by bounded rationality (Simon, 1991). This particularly pertains to the limitation of available information, cognitive limitations related to apprehending the entirety of implications a decision option may have, and the time available for decision making. Regarding the first, the amount of information that would be required for application of SEU-related analyses is hardly ever available in early stage innovation projects that are relevant for this research and related evaluation must hence rely on some kind of forecasting. Research has shown that managers tend to have very low confidence in the reliability of the metrics used for such forecasts and more often than never revert to their gut feeling in decision making (BCG, 2010). The second challenge, which is often ignored in SEU-based evaluation of innovation projects, is that the assessment should be, in its essence, forward-looking. Given the uncertainty related to the impact innovation may have on the market, it requires a longer-term consideration and hypothesizing of "what could be" rather than "what already is". Markets and their current conditions are unlikely to stay the same during the development cycles (often taking years) for multiple reasons. Therefore, we propose that the task of evaluation at the early stages of design should not strictly be about the evaluation of the potential utility of the concept as it presents itself to the decision-maker at the moment when a choice has to be made but about identifying future opportunities with the current design concept only serving as starting point for deeper, future-oriented thinking.

This view on the matter is to some extent reflected in Case-based Decision Theory (CBDT) after Gilboa and Schmeidler (1995) who identified similar shortcomings in SEU. CBDT instead proposes evaluating an option given at a

specific point in time by contrasting it to similar cases from the decision maker's memory in order to determine a sensible course of action. In essence, it dispenses with evaluating forecasts and probabilities and uses analogy building, perceived 'good practice' and re-interpretation of past events to provide meaning and insights into likely outcomes of future events. This is rather intuitive to human beings, simply because when it comes to predicting the future, our brain is set up to make, and favor (Epstude et al., 2016), predictions based on analogy and associations rather than an exhaustive analysis of input properties (Bar, 2009; Baron, 2006). As a consequence, decision makers tend to not analyze towards the future; Instead, heuristics are used to make rather intuitive predictions (Payne et al. 1988; Kahneman et al., 1982). These then provide the input for a subsequent formal and rational analysis intended to 'prove' the initial prediction (Dorst, 2011; Galle, 1996). That means the analysis is then often carried out in a manner that (sub-)consciously favors an already formed viewpoint and the outcome of the analysis becomes somewhat predictable. By extension, it may lead decision makers to search for what they believe to be recurring patterns of (un)successful projects, rather than scrutinizing an innovation potential at hand. Thorough elaboration of the project's future potential thus is precluded. Moreover, changing market conditions are likely to create novel situations for which analogies from the past cannot provide accurate predictions. Finally, a person's recollection of past events is often selective and incomplete leading to erroneous re-interpretation (Loewenstein, 1999). Related decision-making biases are, for instance, optimism and hindsight biases, but also confirmation, endowment, ownership or availability biases. (Eisenbart et al., 2022b, 2022c; Sunstein & Hastie, 2015).

To address and overcome such inherently biased decision-making processes, there is a substantial body of research emerging from the field of design studies on the cognitive strategies of exceptional designers across disciplines (Cross & Cross, 1998). One such strategy, rooted in thinking/reasoning processes germane to Design Thinking, that is particularly relevant to decision-making is future-thinking (which relies on the cognitive processes of abductive reasoning, but also creativity and strategic foresight). In design, abductive reasoning is the formulation/hypothesis of novel scenarios for future developments and the subsequent process of forming an explanatory hypothesis of "what might be". Thereby interplays the essential cognitive processes of divergent/convergent thinking: the desired value creation is known, but the object or service that would produce this value or the conditions under which the object or service operate to produce the desired value would not be known and thus would have to be explored through alternative scenarios. Abductive reasoning helps designers to connect these two (Dorst, 2011). The implication is that such future-oriented reasoning has an effect on decision making and can resolve the discussed decision making-biases favoring the status-quo over (disruptive) innovation.

Seeing the above discussed limitations, we argue that early stage innovation – because of its intrinsic forward-looking nature – lends itself for evaluation following these reasoning processes inherent to Design Thinking. Building on the theoretical considerations discussed in the previous section, we propose future-oriented thinking as an approach to lessen a decision makers susceptibility to common cognitive biases. Effective decision making should strive to identify alternative opportunities, related to the generation and evaluation of potential extensions to or enabled by the proposed design concept, respectively. With this goal in mind, future thinking can be an effective means to foster the generation of alternative hypotheses for future scenarios for a project to have a viable path to market – followed by deductive/inductive scrutiny of these hypotheses – eventually raising the chance of seizing opportunity through innovation. By reducing bias that favor the status quo, it is argued that it aides subjects in getting over their personal risk aversion threshold, allowing more 'good' ideas to pass through the filter. However, studies (Eisenbart et al., 2022a, 2022b; Dong et al. 2015, 2016) show that exposing subjects to future thinking frames does not – in turn – result in an unacceptable high amount of inadequate design ideas being developed into market offerings either. This implies substantial potential of future thinking to improve early stage decision making and innovation management more generally. A possible explanation for these findings is that when subjects were proposing hypotheses about favorable future scenarios for a potential design idea to create value in a future market, each such hypothesis would be scrutinized for logical consistency, either by the subject or by a group an idea is proposed to, for its likelihood to become reality. It would then be explored further or dismissed accordingly. Research by Saaty (2006) suggests that individuals are surprisingly accurate in intuitively evaluating likelihoods of future scenarios, even more so if case they have long-standing experience in the relevant field. Putting these arguments together really speaks to the value of future oriented thinking. Work by Eisenbart et al. (2022b, 2022c) gives initial evidence for the same.

Conclusion

To allow an unbridled invasion of AI into organisations and their interaction or control over society without strong filtering of the harsher elements would be a capitulation to totalitarianism. Design, Design Thinking and the human filter is imperative to reap the benefits of machine learning for the benefit of humanity.

A key concern from design qualified professionals is the competency-based training in design thinking methodology, creating the impression that anybody can practice the methods and utilize the tools.

There is scant evidence of qualitative outcomes over the last decade to quantify benefits of this process. Creativity and Design education has been mined for the purpose of meeting Key Performance Indicators and a true engagement with multi-disciplinary design practice has been avoided. The codesign expression means policy makers are designing policy with rather than to and for service delivery to communities, but communities are unsatisfied that the product of this codesign isn't more than just patronizing authoritarianism.

Pre-emptive moves for ground rules like that of The Department of Industry, Science and Resources (2023) cautionary approach in ethical engagement in AI, as a draft document, could benefit from expert engagement with design thinking, but it would be beneficial for these engagements to be enhanced with a true codesign structure that engages with multidisciplinary teams.

No doubt some 12 months after the release of Chat GPT there are yet to emerge responses and reactions to manage the new order in artificial intelligence within the information technology industry, with lessons learned from user experience and designs role in the enhancing accessibility, design thinking as a process and interdisciplinary design practice will play a significant role in maintaining a civil society.

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